

Importance of Middle Mesial Canal In Permanent Mandibular First Molar - 4 Case Report

Raghavendra Ainapur¹, Amit Pachlag², Sharmila Tapashetti³, Shrinidhi V B⁴

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Associate Professor¹
Department of Conservative Dentistry
SDM College of Dental Sciences & Hospital
Dharwad
A Constituent unit of Shri Dharmasthala
Manjunatheshwara University.

Professor²
Department of Conservative Dentistry
SDM College of Dental Sciences & Hospital
Dharwad
A constituent unit of Shri Dharmasthala
Manjunatheshwara University.

Associate Professor³
Department of Conservative Dentistry
SDM College of Dental Sciences & Hospital
Dharwad
A Constituent Unit Of Shri Dharmasthala
Manjunatheshwara University.

Professor⁴
Department of Conservative Dentistry
St. Joseph College of Dental Sciences
Eluru

Abstract

With better understanding of the morphology of root canals, the variation in root canal anatomy can be easily found. Careful clinical examination along with radiograph interpretation enables the clinician to successfully treat such cases. The pulp and/or necrotic tissue can be source for the persistence of Periapical lesion. This article reports 4 cases of middle mesial canal in the permanent mandibular molar. The middle mesial canal in all three cases were detected without aid of operating microscope. This case report shows that a careful clinical and radiographic examination is of utmost importance to treat the aberrant internal anatomy.

Keywords - Mandibular First Molar, Middle Mesial Canal,

Introduction

From early work by Hess and Zucher (1) in 1925 through to more recent studies demonstrating the anatomical complexities of the root canal, roots with a conical channel and a single apical foramen have been known to be the exception rather than the rule. Although all teeth are anatomically complex, first lower molars are the first permanent posterior teeth to erupt and are those that most often suffer from caries, so they are highly likely to require endodontic treatment. These molars normally have two roots, one mesial and one distal, and their usual canal distribution is two in the mesial root and one or two in the distal root. Nonetheless, other possibilities exist.

The presence of an independent middle mesial canal with a separate orifice and a separate apical foramen was reported in 1974 by Vertucci and Williams (2) and Barker et al. (3). In addition, cases with three canals in the distal root and two in the mesial root (4), two canals in the mesial root and three canals in three distal roots (5), two canals in the distolingual root (6), two roots and one canal in each (7), Four canals in mesial root of mandibular molar (8), molar with seven canals: 2 mesiobuccal, 2 mesiolingual and 3 distal canals (9) were reported in the literature.

The presence of a third canal in the mesial root of mandibular first molars has been reported to have an incidence rate of 1 to 15%.

This additional canal may have a separate foramen, or join apically with either the mesiobuccal or mesiolingual canal⁽¹⁰⁾.

The purpose of this article is to report the successful treatment of four cases of a mandibular first molar with three mesial canals

Case Report 1

A 17-year old male patient presented with a non-contributory medical history, a chief complaint of pain in the lower left back tooth region. There was a history of periodic discomfort to biting on the tooth. Clinical exam revealed large occlusal caries in left mandibular first molar and delayed response to electric pulp test. Radiographic examination revealed involvement of pulp with no Periapical radiolucency. Root canal treatment was indicated. Access cavity was prepared with No 4 round bur (Mani). The coronal pulp tissue was removed and the chamber irrigated with 5% sodium hypochlorite solution. Three root canal orifices were detected, two mesial and large distal. Since the patient was of young age middle mesial canal was not ruled out. Exploring the fissure between the main mesial canals, with a sharp endodontic explorer, a "stick" was encountered. A small pre-curved file (size .08 Flexofile, Dentsply Maillefer, Germany) was inserted into the middle

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mesial canal orifice. With clockwise and counterclockwise rotational movements, the instrument was advanced until working length was achieved. The working lengths were estimated using an apex locator (Root ZX, Morita, Tokyo, Japan) and then confirmed with a radiograph. Three separate mesial root canals were confirmed with a radiograph (Figure 3). During instrumentation, the middle mesial canal joined the mesiobuccal canal. All the mesial canals were instrumented with protaper rotary files and the distal canal was enlarged upto 45 k file size. All canals were dried and filled by cold lateral condensation of gutta-percha with a zinc-oxide eugenol sealer. (Figure 4).

Case Report 2

A 31-yr-old woman complained about high sensitivity to cold stimuli, and pain caused by chewing, located to the left mandibular region. Once the pain was elicited it persisted for several minutes. Tooth 36 had an distocclusal caries. The tooth was painful to percussion, and thermal tests gave exaggerated responses compared to proximal and contralateral teeth. The diagnosis of irreversible pulpitis was made and single visit endodontic treatment scheduled. After anaesthesia, an adequate access preparation was made. On removal of roof of pulp chamber bleeding was excessive. 3% sodium hypochlorite was used to dissolve the pulp. Two mesial and two distal canal orifices were found and pulp extirpated with .No 15 K-files. Slight bleeding was evident each time file was inserted into mesiobuccal canal. A first working length measurement radiograph was taken using digital radiography. The files in all canals were 0.5 mm short of apex. Since the bleeding didn't stop search was undertaken to see for the presence of middle mesial canal. Once the negotiation of the third canal was done, a second working length radiograph was taken. The radiograph confirmed the middle mesial canal and it was joining with the mesiobuccal canal (fig 5). The two distal canals presented as two separate orifices and two separate apical foramen. The three mesial canals were enlarged using protaper rotary files up to size of F1 and distal canal up to F2 using a crown-down approach. Master cone radiograph was taken to confirm the exactness of the preparation (fig 6). Irrigation was made using copious amounts of 1% sodium hypochlorite. The canals were finally washed with sterile saline and dried with sterile paper cones. The three canals were obturated using the lateral condensation technique and a AH Plus sealer. After removal of excess gutta-percha cones, the access closed with temporary cement. An angled radiograph was taken to confirm the quality of obturation (fig 7). The patient was recalled after two weeks. The patient was asymptomatic. The temporary restoration removed and restored with composite resin.

Case 3

A 27-year-old female patient was referred to the dental clinic for endodontic treatment of tooth #36. The patient's chief complaint was pain in his lower left back teeth region. Clinical examinations revealed that tooth had deep bucco-occlusal caries. The tooth was tender to vertical percussion but not to palpation and the periodontal condition of the tooth was normal and no pocketing was observed. On sensitivity tests, using heated gutta-percha, there was a severe, long-lasting painful response. The reason of his pain was diagnosed to be irreversible pulpitis in his mandib-

ular left first molar. The preoperative radiograph revealed presence of Radix Entomolarix. The left inferior alveolar nerve was anaesthetized using 2% Lidocaine with 1:80000 adrenaline (Daroupakhsh, Tehran, Iran). After an adequate access preparation was made, two mesial and two distal canal orifices were found. Examining the fissure connecting the two mesial canals carefully, the tip of a #08 file could be inserted into a spot located in the middle of the distance between the two mesial canals. The middle mesial canal originated as a separate orifice but joined to the mesiobuccal canal in the apical third of the canal (fig 8). The working length radiograph confirmed the presence of two distal root and single canal in each.. The root canals were cleaned and shaped using protaper rotary files using crown down approach. The root canals were copiously irrigated with 1% sodium hypochlorite solution. Before obturation, master points were seated to test their suitability to canals (fig 9). Then, the canals were dried with sterilized paper points and obturated with protaper gutta-percha and zinc oxide sealer (fig 10).

Case Report 4

A 25 year old male patient came to the dental clinic with complaint of pain on biting in the left mandibular region. On examination deep occlusal caries was noted in the mandibular left first molar. The tooth was tender on percussion and negative sign for mobility and sinus tract. The electric pulp testing gave a delayed response. The pre-operative radiograph revealed carious involvement of pulp with slight widening of periodontal ligament space (fig). A diagnosis of apical periodontitis was established. A two visit endodontic treatment was planned. Once anesthesia was achieved, access cavity was prepared under rubber dam. Considering the age of the patient, the floor of the pulp chamber was searched for the presence of three mesial canals. Probing the fissure between the two mesial canals, a stick was encountered. #10 file was introduced into canal. A total of five root canal orifices were located (fig) and working length radiograph was taken. The radiograph revealed the middle mesial canal joining the mesiolingual canal (fig). The preparation was carried out using step-down technique and apical area enlarged up to #30 k-file for the mesial canals. During the coronal flaring of the distal canal the partition between the two distal canal was removed and treated as single canal and was enlarged up to #45 k-file. An intracanal medicament of calcium hydroxide was placed and appointment was scheduled after one week. Patient returned with no symptoms and no tender on vertical percussion. The temporary restoration was removed and the canal was dry. Master cone was selected and confirmatory radiograph was taken (fig). The obturation of the root canal was carried out using AH Plus sealer and gutta-percha using lateral compaction technique (fig).

Discussion

Based on the literature and these clinical cases, it is evident that knowledge of the anatomical variations of the mandibular molars is extremely important for the success of endodontic treatment. According to Cohen and Burns (11), canals are often not treated because they are not located. At the same time clinician should keep in mind the aberrant anatomy and search for the extracanal at the time of canal detection and their negotiation. For this to accomplish, proper access cavity preparation and angled

radiograph are very much necessary.

There are many variations in the root canal morphology of mandibular molar. One among them is the middle mesial canal. It has also called by other names - intermediate canal⁽¹²⁾, mesio-centric canal⁽¹³⁾.

Many authors agree on the presence of three foramina in the mesial root but few report three independent canals, which presents itself as a rare anatomical variant^(14,15). Goel⁽¹⁶⁾ notes that the mesial root of permanent mandibular first molars presented two foramina in 60% of the specimens they examined, 6.7% had three and 3.3% even had four. According to Mortman⁽¹⁷⁾, the third mesial canal is not an extra canal but rather the sequelae of instrumenting the isthmus between the mesiobuccal and mesiolingual canals.

While a third canal in the mesial root of mandibular first molars may not be a very frequent discovery, a review of the literature indicates that its prevalence is 0-15% (Table 1).

The middle mesial canal must be sought along the line between the two mesial canals after deroofing of the pulp chamber and of any cervical stenosis in this zone that might cover the opening of the canals, using burs. A round bur or an ultrasonic tip can be used for removal of any protuberance from the mesial axial wall which would prevent direct access to the developmental groove between MB and ML orifices. This developmental groove should be carefully checked with the sharp tip of an endodontic explorer. If depression or orifices are located, the groove can be troughed with ultrasonic tips at its mesial aspect until a small file can negotiate this intermediate canal⁽¹⁸⁾.

The detection of additional root canals requires a careful clinical and radiographic inspection. Diagnostic tools such as multiple radiographs, careful examination of the pulpal floor with a sharp explorer, and better visualization using an operating microscope^(19, 20) are all important aids in the detection of additional root canals. Recently, various attempts have been made to use CT imaging for the confirmatory diagnosis of morphologic aberrations in the endodontic field⁽²¹⁾.

Conclusion

In conclusion, every attempt should be made to find and treat all root canals to ensure successful endodontic treatment. The importance of an accurate clinical evaluation of root canal number and morphology in mandibular molars cannot be overemphasized. Some points which may help in recognizing the presence of middle mesial canal are –

- The presence of bleeding in one of the mesial canal after pulp extirpation
- Pain didn't subside after the initial appointment. Other cause of pain should be ruled out.
- The mesiobuccal and mesiolingual canal are widely spaced
- Presence of pain during instrumentation of either mesiobuccal or mesiolingual canal
- The patient's age less than 30 should always be searched for middle mesial canal.
- Large occlusal table and wider faciolingually.

- Diagnostic radiographs are of limited use in identification of middle mesial canal. Only careful clinical evaluation with magnification can help to identify the extra canal.
- Always probe the fissure between the two mesial canals. A stick may be encountered if the middle mesial canal orifice is present.

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1a – Clinical Picture

1e – Post Obturation Radiograph

1b – Preop Radiograph

2a – Preop Radiograph

1c – Working Length Radiograph

2b – Working Length Radiograph

1d – Mastercone Radiograph

2c – Mastercone Radiograph

2d – Post Obturation Radiograph

4a – Working Length Radiograph

3a – Working Length Radiograph

4b – Mastercone Radiograph

3b – Mastercone Radiograph

4c – Post Obturation Radiograph

3c – Post Obturation Radiograph

Author	Number of Clinical Case(s)	Materials And Methods	Number of canals and number of foramina (of both mesial and distal canals)	Type of canal preparation	Obturation	Type
Weine (7)(1982)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 1 foramina Distal root – 1 canal and 1 foramina	Not mentioned	Lateral compaction technique with Wach's paste as sealer	<p>All three canals joined apically</p>
Mortman and Sunghhee (8) (2003)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 1 foramina Distal root – 2 canals and 1 foramina	Not mentioned	Lateral compaction technique with sealapex	
Min (9) (2004)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 1 foramina Distal root – 2 canals and 1 foramina			
Martinez Berna and Badanelli (10) (1985)	2	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 3foramina Distal root – 3 canals and 1 foramina	Not mentioned	Lateral condensed guttapercha and AHPlus sealer	<p>3-3 all three canals independent</p>
Bond et al (11) (1988)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 3 foramina Distal root – 2 canals and 2 foramina	Not mentioned	Laterally condensed guttapercha and Roth 801 Sealer	
Jacobsen (12) (1994)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 3 foramina Distal root – 2 canals and 2 foramina	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	
Ricucci (13) (1997) (intermediate canal)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 3 foramina Distal root – 2 canals and 1 foramina	Step down technique	Lateral compaction technique	
Holtzman (14) (1997)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 3 foramina Distal root – 2 canals and 1 foramina			
Yesilsoy et al (15)(2009)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 3 foramina			
La et al (16) (2010)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Distal root (2) – 2 canals and 2 foramina			
Poorni et al (17)(2010)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph) & CBCT Images	Mesial root – 3 canals and 3 foramina Distal root (2) – 2 canals and 2 foramina	Protaper rotary instruments	Gutta-percha and AHPlus sealer	
	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 3 foramina Distal root – 2 canals and 1 foramina	Crown-down technique with protaper rotary files	Lateral compaction technique with zinc oxide eugenol sealer	

Fabra Campos (18) (1985)	3	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 2 foramina Distal root – 2 canals and 1 foramina		Lateral compaction technique	<p>3-2 Middle mesial canal joining mesiobuccal canal</p>
Fabra Campos (19) (1989)	13	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 2 foramina Distal root – 2 canals and 1 foramina			
Jacobsen et al (12)(1994)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 2 foramina Distal root – 2 canals ; not mentioned about foramina	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	
Mortman and Sunghhee (8) (2003)	2	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 2 foramina Distal root – 2 canals and 1 foramina			
Baugh and Wallace (20) (2004)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 2 foramina Distal root – 2 canals and 2 foramina		Laterally condensed gutta-percha and Roth 801 Sealer	
Fabra Campos (18) (1985) (intermediate canal)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 2 foramina Distal root – 2 canals and 2 foramina		Lateral compaction technique	<p>3-2 Middle mesial canal joining Mesiolingual canal</p>
Fabro Campos (19) (1989)	6	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 2 foramina Distal root – 2 canals and 1 foramina			
Jacobsen et al (12) (1994) (mesio-centric canal)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 2 foramina Distal root – 2 canals ; not mentioned about foramina	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	
DeGrood and Cunningham (21) (1997)	1	In vivo (PA radiograph)	Mesial root – 3 canals and 2 foramina Distal root – 2 canals and 2 foramina		Laterally condensed gutta-percha and Roth 801 Sealer	

Table 1 - Case Reports of A Third Canal In The Mesial Root of Mandibular First Molars

Authors	Year	No. of teeth	Method	Three canals(%)
Vertucci (22)	1974	100	Vitro	1
Pomeranz (23)	1981	100	Vivo	12
Martinez-Berna and Badanelli (24)	1983	1418	Vivo	1.5
Fabra-Campos (18)	1985	145	Vivo	2.1
Fabra-Campos (19)	1989	760	Vivo	2.6
Goel (25)	1991	60	Vivo	15
Caliskan et al. (26)	1995	100	Vitro	3.39%
Wasti et al (27)	2001	30	Vitro	3.3%
Sarkar S (28)	2002	10	Vitro	70%
Navarro LF (29)	2007	27	Vitro	14.81%
Shahriar Shahi (30)	2008	209	Vitro	0.95%
Chen G (31)	2009	183	Vitro	6%
A. A. Al-Qudah & L. A. Awawdeh (32)	2009	330	Vitro	6%

Table 2- Prevalence of A Third Canal tn the Mesial Root of Mandibular First Molars According to Different Authors

Author/year	Percentage of two distal root	Percentage of distal canals	Population
Taylor (1899) (33)	3.4	–	United kingdom
Tratman (1938) (34)	5.8	–	Chinese
Skidmore AE, Bjorndal AM (1971) (35)	2.2%	28.9%	Caucasians
Turner (1971) (36)	32%	-	American Indian
Curzon MEJ (1973) (37)	3.4%	-	United kingdom
Fabra-Campos (1985) (18)	Not mentioned	49.60%-2 canals	Not mentioned
Yones et al (1990) (38)	2.92	Not studied	Saudi people of Asiatic and Africa descendant
Loh (1990) (39)	7.2	Not studied	Singaporean Chinese
Goel NK, Gill KS, Taneja JR.(1991) (25)	1.7%	40% - 2 canals; 1.7% - 3 canals	Indian population
Ferraz JAB, Pécora JD (1992) (40)	11.4%		Japanese
Yew and Chan (1993) 41)	21.5%	31.5%-2 canals	Chinese
Caliskan et al.(1995) (26)	Not mentioned	1.69% - 3 canals 16.94%- 2 canals	Turkish population
Sperber GH, Moreau J (1998) (42)	3.12%	25% - 2 canals	Sengalese
Zaatar EI, al Anizi SA, al Duwairi Y.(1998) (43)	–	26.5% - 2 canals	Kuwaitis population
al-Nazhan S.1999 (44)	5.97%	57.76%-2 canals	Saudi arabian sub-population
Gulabivala K, Aung TH, Alavi A, Ng YL(2001) (45)	10%	38.4% - 2 canals	Burmese population
Wasti F, Shearer AC, Wilson NH. (2001) (27)	Not mentioned in the study	50%- 2 canals	South asian pakistanis population
Gulabivala K, Opananon A, Ng YL, Alavi A (2002) (46)	12.7%	30.5% - 2 canals 3.4% - 3 canals	Thai population
Ahmed HA, Abu-bakr NH, Yahia NA, Ibrahim YE. (2007) (47)	3%	59% - 2 canals	Sudanese population

Peiris R, Takahashi M, Sasaki K, Kanazawa E. (2007) (48)	3%	Most of them presented with 2 canals	Srilankan population
Ruwan Duminda Jayasinghe, Thomas Ka-Lun Li (2007) (49)	22%	Not mentioned	Hong Kong
Pattanshetti N, Gaidhane M, Al Kandari AM. (2008) (50)	4%	49%-2 distal canals	Kuwait population
Shahriar Shahi (2008) (30)	1.44	34.43% - 2 distal canals	Iraninan
Al-Qudah AA, Awawdeh LA.(2009) (32)	4%	46% - 2 distal canals 1%- 3 distal canals	Jordian population
Chen G, Yao H, Tong C. (2009) (31)	20%	46% - 2 canals	Taiwan population
Rwenyonyi CM, Kutesa A, Muwazi LM, Buwembo W (2009) (51)		23.2% – 2 canals	Uganda population
Song JS, Kim SO, Choi BJ, Choi HJ, Son HK, Lee JH.(2009) (52)	33.1%	Not studied	Korean children
Edgar Schäfer, Dominik Breuer, and Sabine Janzen. (2009) (53)	1.35%	Not studied	German
Chen YC, Lee YY, Pai SF, Yang SF. (2009) (54)	9.9%	Not studied	Taiwanese population
Tu et al (2009) (55)	33.33%	Not mentioned	Taiwanese population
Huang CC, Chang YC, Chuang MC, Lai TM, Lai JY, Lee BS, Lin CP (2010) (56)	25.3%	40.5%-2 canals	Taiwanese individual
Song JS, Choi HJ, Jung IY, Jung HS, Kim SO. (2010) (57)	24.5%		
Garg et al (2010) (58)	5.95%	Not mentioned	Indian

Table 3- Prevalence of Three Rooted Mandibular First Molars- Survey of Available Studies

Author	Year	No of Distal Root	No of Distal Canals
Stroner WF, Remeikis NA, Carr GB (59)	1984	2	DB-2 DL-1
Beatty RG, Interian CM (60)	1985	2	DB-2 DL-1
Quackenbush LE (61)	1986	2	DB-2 DL-1
Friedman S, Moshonov J, Stabholz A (62)	1986	3	DB-1 Distal centre-1 DL-1
Reeh ES. (63)	1998	1	DB-1 Distal center - 1 DL-1
Kimura Y, Matsumoto K (64)	2000	2	DB-2 DL-1
Segura-Egea JJ (65)	2002		DB-1 DL-1
Se Yeh and HL Huang (66)	2003		DB- 1 DL-2
De Moor RJG, Deroose CAJG, Calberson FLG (67) (4 case reports)	2004	2	DB-1 DL-1
Lee et al (68)	2006	3	DB-1 Distal centre-1 DL-1
Ghoddusi J, Naghavi N, Zarei M, Rohani E (69)	2007	2	DB-2 Distal centre-1 DL-1
Barletta et al (70)	2007	2	DB-1 DL-2
Calberson et al. (71) (2 case reports)	2007	2	
Ming-Gene Tu (72)	2009		DB-1 DL-1
Parolia A (1)	2009		DB-1 DL-1
Chandra et al (73)	2009	1	DB-1 Distal center - 1 DL-1
Pragati Mirikar, Arvind Shenoy, and Goud K Mallikarjun (74)	2009	1	DB-1 DL-1

Table 4 - Previous Reports Concerning Radix Entomolaris and Number of Distal Canals

Author	Year
Barnett F (75)	1986
R. TedRice and Buford O.Gilbert Jr (76)	1987
Bolger and Schindler (77)	1988

Table 6 - Case Reports of C-shape Canal in Mandibular Molar

Author	Year	Population	Prevalence	Method of study
Keene (78)	1966	Americians of European origin	2.8% - hypotaurodontism 0.4%- mesotaurodontism	Biometric study
Blumberg et al (79)	1971	Negros and white American patients	2.5%	Biometric study
Shifman A. (80)	1978	Israelians	5.6%	Periapical and bitewing radiographs
Jorgenson et al. (81)	1982	African American children	4.37%	Panoramic radiographs
Ruprecht et al. (82)	1987	Saudi Arabians	11.3%	Panoramic radiographs
Mac Donald –Jankowski and Li (83)	1993	Chinese	46.4%	Panoramic radiographs
Sarr et al. (84)	2000	Senegalese	48%	Panoramic radiographs
Park et al. (85)	2006	Korean	3.9%	Clinical and radiographic examination

Table - Studies Done on Taurodontism of Mandibular Molars

Author	Year	Highlight of the Study
Hamner JE et al. (86)	1964	Hypertaurodontism involving the permanent dentition of a 13-year-old American Caucasian girl
Cesar A. Mena (87)	1971	Familial trait in afro-american children
Goldstein E and Gottlieb MA (88)	1973	Demonstrated familial tendencies for taurodontism
A. Shifman and A. Buchner (89)	1976	Taurodontism a more common entity than previous thought. Explained clinical aspects regarding endodontic and periodontic therapy
Sathyanarayan R (90)	2001	
Tiku et al (91)	2003	
Ashwin R and Arathi R.(92)	2006	Presented a case of taurodontism involving deciduous lower second molars and all permanent first molar .

Table – Case Reports on Taurodontism